

APPLICATION OF CAMEL MODEL IN LIFE INSURANCE BUSINESS IN NIGERIA

(A Case Study of Five Life Insurance Businesses in Nigeria)

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ABSTRACT

In practically all developed and emerging countries, insurance has become a significant and thriving element of the financial services sector. Insurance is a risk financing mechanism that, if adequately managed, could contribute to economic development and effective resource allocation. The advantage of risk transfer via insurance services might effectively assist in lowering transaction costs, providing liquidity, and facilitating investment economies of scale. Thus, this study applied CAMEL [Capital adequacy, Asset quality, Reinsurance and Actuarial issues, Management soundness, Earnings/Profitability, Liquidity] Model to investigate the performance of insurance companies in Nigeria. Using the financial soundness ratio indicator for the selected five life insurance companies, there is a significant difference in the capital adequacy of the life insurance company being considered and there is also a significant difference in liquidity of the five considered life insurance companies in Nigeria. Based on the performance metric, LEADWAY INSURANCE is preferred based on the soundness indicators. This research work indicates that the CAMEL model can be adequately used to test the financial soundness of the life insurance business.

Keywords: *IMF, CAMEL, Capital Adequacy, Asset Quality, and Reinsurance.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Nigeria's insurance industry is a vital aspect of the country's economy. Insurance and reinsurance firms are companies that offer or provide insurance coverage to the general population. Insurance firms (insurers) accept insurable risks in exchange for a monetary payment called a premium, which is the primary source of insurance money (Igbodika, Ibenta & John, 2016; Madukwe & Obi-Nweke, 2014; Ubom, 2014). As a result, it is projected that the insurance sector's activities as a supplier of insurance coverages would influence economic growth. The insurance industry also contributes to economic growth by mobilizing savings and investable money generated through premiums and underwriting profits and making them available to capital and other financial markets (Oke, 2012; Olayungbo, 2015; Yinusa & Akinlo, 2010).

Insurance has become an important and thriving aspect of financial services and if properly administered, insurance is a saving mechanism that may help enhance economic growth and contribute to effective resource allocation. The benefit of risk transfer through insurance services might effectively lower transaction costs, provide liquidity, and facilitate investment economies of scale. It's difficult to assess the financial health of an individual insurer or the insurance industry as a whole. As a result, a company's total financial performance is influenced by a variety of elements, some of which are difficult to define, such as managerial quality, organizational structure, and system control. A team presented a study at the International Monetary Fund (IMF) that looked at insurance as a source of the financial system vulnerability and identified key indicators that might be used to monitor the financial soundness of insurance businesses as a whole due to risk factors. As a result, the IMF's working paper proposed two sets of metrics for assessing the financial soundness of life and non-life insurance companies: core and encouraged.

In the IMF Background paper, significant Financial Soundness Indicators (FSIs) for financial institutions, including both life and non-life insurance, were recommended (2003). The paper presented a CAMELS [Capital adequacy, Asset quality, Reinsurance, and Actuarial issues, Management soundness, Earnings/Profitability, Liquidity, and Sensitivity to Market Risk] Framework that includes several different ratios with the use of those quantitative factors that affect the financial position of the insurance company. The application of different ratio analyses to describe the financial state of insurance organizations is explored in this model.

Jegade, 2005 shows that in Nigeria, the first such firms began in 1918 when the East and West African trading companies introduced the Royal Exchange Assurance Agency (Jegade, 2005). Other firms include Patterson Zochonis, Liverpool, London and Globe, BEWAC's legal and General Assurance, and the Law Union and Rock.

A contract between an insurance policyholder and an insurance firm is known as life insurance. If something bad happens to the covered individual, the insurer pays the grieving family the whole amount, which includes the sum promised plus the bonus. If there is no danger, the insured person will pay the whole matured amount after the given term. Life insurance also protects the interests of persons with diminishing wages as they become older, people who suffer accidents, and retired people. There are several policies available today both in the public and commercial sectors to meet the needs of various insurance holders. When compared to other investment options, life insurance policies provide superior returns. The majority of life insurance plans include bonuses that no other investment plan can match. Life insurance money is secure and protects against hazards. The money invested will earn a fair return and will be reimbursed in full as the sum promised either at the end of the period or when the insured passes away. Other advantages of investing in life insurance include tax advantages, financing choices, life stage planning, and guaranteed income benefits, among others.

Nigeria has 58 insurance businesses, 16 of which are life insurance companies and 42 of which are non-life insurance companies, according to the National Insurance Commission (NAICOM). Many more buyers have emerged in Nigeria as a result of increased consumer knowledge of the benefits and relevance of insurance and reinsurance. Aside from new distribution channels, such as brokers, bank assurance, the Internet, and corporate agents, life insurance clients now have more options for goods and services.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Insurance firms are in the main business of managing risk for people and corporations, which necessitates a thorough examination of the numerous aspects impacting financial performance. So, different financial indicators are well explained in the CAMELS model for analyzing the working of insurance companies, which helps in analyzing the capital adequacy, asset quality, reinsurance and actuarial issues, management soundness, earnings/profitability, liquidity, and sensitivity to market risk of insurance companies under various ratios. It assists the analyst in more effectively studying the financial status of the insurance business, comparing the financial performance of one insurance company to another, and displaying the firm's growth tendencies.

RESEARCH QUESTION & HYPOTHESIS

The questions to be considered at the course of this study based on the objectives are:

- Which life insurance company ranks the highest in financial soundness?
- Is there any significant difference in the capital adequacy of life insurance companies in Nigeria?
- Is there any significant difference in the liquidity of the insurance companies in Nigeria?

The following stated hypotheses will be tested:

- H_{01} : There is no significant difference in the capital adequacy of the considered life insurance companies in Nigeria
- H_{02} : There is no significant difference in the liquidity of the considered life insurance companies in Nigeria

OBJECTIVE OF STUDY

The main objective of this study is to use the CAMEL model to assess the financial soundness of life insurance businesses in Nigeria. The particular goals are to:

- Use the CAMEL model to rate the financial soundness of the considered life insurance companies in Nigeria.
- Compare and contrast the capital adequacy of the considered life insurance companies in Nigeria.
- Conduct a comparative analysis of the considered Nigerian life insurance industry's liquidity.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The name "life" insurance is partly accurate, but somewhat euphemistic because it refers to insurances in which the covered event is tied to the insured's death. This is determined by the type of the issue and can fall into one of two categories:

- a. A death's occurrence,
- b. The absence of death from one's life.

As a result, we have two basic insurances that are critical in many ways: Term insurance (for death) and pure endowment insurance (for living through). This research will continue to refer to life insurance as solely those insurances that can be defined by these two insured occurrences in the

future parts, but note that this conceptual clarity is difficult to maintain for two reasons. Which are:

Tradition is a multi-layered concept. To begin with, life insurance has generally included both accidental and health coverage. Although these are not technically considered life insurance, they are treated as such in practice. On the other hand, there are two dangers that do not match the criteria of an insurable risk, although they do emerge in life insurance contracts from time to time. Marriage and childbirth are two of them. Even European Union standards acknowledge this heritage and permit the development of life insurance plans that include these risks under the life insurance branch. In any case, we don't deal with these two risks here.

The evolution of life insurance products has led to the old auxiliary purpose of life insurance, long-term saving, becoming the primary function in many products, and there is no element that can be identified as a covered "event" in these policies. The book will treat these products as full-rights life insurance, and does not require that a life insurance policy include one of the above-mentioned covered occurrences.

As with property-casualty insurances, life insurance cannot be reimbursing insurance, which means that if the covered event occurs, the amount of reimbursement given by the insurer is decided by an evaluation of damage based on the extent of the actual loss. Even the use of the phrase "claim" in reference to a life insurance insured event might be questioned, as this term was designed primarily to represent tangible, or manifested damages. Of course, if the insured event occurs, the parties to a life insurance contract will suffer losses, but these are less tangible (if the insured event is living through the insurance term) and appear through more transpositions (if the insured event is death during the insurance term) than in the case of traditional reimbursing insurance.

In terms of reserving, life insurances (at least 99 percent of them) are completely different from all other forms of insurance, including non-life insurance (at least from 99 percent of these). The reason for this is due to the average length of insurance periods and whether or not there is a distinct, unambiguous shift in the likelihood of a claim during the term. So, let's have a look at the differences between the two types of insurance described above in these areas. A standard life insurance policy has a duration of several years, if not decades. The mortality rate rises steadily over time, and the actual death rate is generally near the theoretically predicted value for the entire portfolio with very minor fluctuations. As a result of this, and the fact that – unlike property-casualty insurance – only one claim may arise throughout the term of life insurance, the insurer utilizes the premiums received during the period to pay claims, hence the majority of the premiums must be set aside, or reserved. As a result, a life insurance company's reserves are long-term and stable. Consider property-casualty insurance, which is a type of non-life insurance. Unlike life insurance, property-casualty insurance coverage is normally signed for a year (even if it is generally automatically prolonged in the next year). The risk is largely ignored in the next year, with the exception of a few exceptional elements that are the same as the prior year. As a result, there is no need to build up a reserve from received premiums (at least not to the degree as in the case of life insurance). In the case of property-casualty insurance, a given year's claims are usually covered by the same year's premium. The variation of claims, on the other hand, is, in contrast to life insurance, extremely variable. Because of the aforementioned distinctions, we divide insurance into two categories (according to EU guidelines): life and non-life. The problem is also addressed in the Hungarian Act on Insurers and Insurance Activities. The life/non-life distinction has an

organizational implication: in many countries, insurance firms that deal with both life and non-life insurance are unable to function.

In a term insurance contract, the insurer assumes obligation for the contractor's (policyholder's) premium payment by paying an amount stated in advance (sum insured) to the person indicated in advance (beneficiary) if the person specified in advance dies (insured) during a set time period (insurance term). The insurance policy is cancelled without benefit payment if the insured survives to the end of the insurance period. It's worth taking a closer look at this definition because it contains a lot of keywords that we may utilize later. First and foremost, a life insurance policy's characters (or subjects). There are four of them, as the definition indicates: The insurer, the insurance policyholder, the insured and the beneficiary.

Taking the insurer as an example, the following information about the others is required: The policyholder is the person who signs and pays the insurance policy's premiums. He is the "owner" of the insurance policy (he "holds the policy"), and he has the authority to make legal representations about it, identify the beneficiary, and cancel the policy (surrender). A natural person or a legal entity might be the policyholder. As a natural person, he is typically, but not always, also the insured, and can, of course, also be the beneficiary. Nonetheless, it's important to note if the policyholder, insured, or beneficiary are all the same individuals. When this role is unimportant, or when the same statement may be made for numerous roles, the policy's location is only relevant in comparison to the insurer, and we can use the word client). The policyholder is the principal character of the life insurance contract from a legal standpoint (naturally beside the insurer). The insurance policy covers an occurrence that occurs in the insured person's life. He is the main character in the insurance sense, and he can only be a natural person. If the policyholder and the insured are not the same person, the policy must be signed by the insured before it may take effect. However, from a legal standpoint, this is essentially his only option. Aside from that, the policyholder has the right to take his position as the policyholder if he wishes to surrender the insurance. We must emphasize that the fact that the basic nature of the insurance policy differs from an insurance technical and legal standpoint might cause complications, particularly when interpreting the topic of tax allowances if the state encourages life insurance through tax credits. If the covered event happens, the beneficiary receives the benefits provided by the insurer. He is in the most advantageous position in many ways, since he has no liabilities and only rights, but his position is the least solid. The policyholder has the ability to change the beneficiary at any time, even if the previous beneficiary is unaware of the change. Naturally, the recipient does not have to be a single person or a living being.

If we look at the definition again, the term is the following keyword. The majority of life insurance plans have a set duration, however they can also have an infinite length. Policies with a fixed period normally last for a year or more. These years normally do not coincide with calendar years, but rather begin with the signing of the policy, and the so-called insurance anniversary falls on the same day every year. The minimum length of definite term insurances is typically 5 years, with the maximum term ranging between 25 and 40 years, depending on the firm. In Hungary, the most common duration is 15 years; in more developed countries, it is usually longer. A maximum age limit based on the insured's age is also commonly employed, for example, the insured cannot be older than 75 years old when the policy matures. Indefinite-term life insurance plans normally expire when the policyholder dies or surrenders the policy. In some forms, the predicted termination event is death (for example, in whole-life insurance plans), whereas, in others, it is surrender (essentially in unit-linked policies with no term). The sum insured is the final significant

word. Because life insurance is essentially summed insurance, stating it in this manner is critical. Depending on how many insured occurrences are permitted, a life insurance policy can possibly have more than one marked sum insured. We may talk about pure endowment (and accidental death, accidental disability, and so on...) amounts insured in this way. These might be the same, but they could also be completely different.

(Black and Skipper, 2000); there are three main types of life insurance policies in actuarial literature. They are:

- Whole life insurance - which provides a death benefit for a lifetime;
- Term life insurance - that provides a death benefit for a limited number of years and,
- Endowment life insurance -which is a term life insurance with a saving component.

In general, life insurance is a risk management tool and a savings vehicle for individuals. It also has significant psychological and societal implications. Hofstede (1995) wrote that 'the main function of life insurance is to safeguard against financial loss from the loss of human life'. It also covers the risks of disability, severe sickness, and retirement, in addition to mortality. Sayin, 2003 concluded that life insurance is based on the notion of human life worth.

Black and Skipper, 2000; the economic component of human life is the emphasis of the human life value approach. Any occurrence that influences a person's earning capability has an impact on that person's human life worth. Premature death, infirmity, retirement, or unemployment are examples of such events. Browne and Kim, 1993, the conceptual foundation for life insurance is the human life value idea, which is a product meant to safeguard an individual against two unique risks: premature death and retirement. As a result, while death itself is not a threat, the moment of death is. For most people, death at any age may be deemed premature if it occurs before enough financial provisions have been made for dependants' future financial needs. Black and Skipper, 2000; As a result, life insurance becomes a tool for ensuring a steady source of income to the beneficiaries. Omar and Owusu- Frimpong, 2006; in this perspective, life insurance might be viewed as a savings vehicle, a financial investment, or a risk management tool.

Charumathi (2012) investigated the elements that influence the profitability of Indian life insurers. The research looked at 22 public and 22 private actors over three years, from 2008-09 to 2010-11. Regression analysis was used to achieve the goal, and it was discovered that life insurer profitability was favorably driven by size and liquidity, but adversely influenced by leverage, premium growth, and equity capital. Kumari (2013) looked studied the public and private life insurance industries' financial performance. Various metrics were addressed for this purpose, including the number of life insurance firms, private sector offices, insurance penetration and density, premium revenue growth, and the size of the insurance market. Financial success was measured using a variety of financial ratios. According to the findings, the overall business performance of the Indian life insurance sector improved significantly following privatization.

Ansari, R.Babu, and Murthy (2009) investigated the Life Insurance Corporation's performance. The Life Insurance Corporation of India (LIC) has been experiencing fierce competition from new entrants as a result of globalization of financial services and economic liberalization, and it is also playing a leading role in the life insurance business. Due to direct competition from private players, LIC has been compelled to develop a successful marketing strategy that includes innovative products and improved customer service to please existing and prospective policyholders. Both sectors must intensify competition and create a win-win situation for both sides to boost insurance

density and penetration levels in order to meet consumer wants and expectations of the Indian insurance industry.

Gulati and Jain (2011) examined the commercial performance of all life insurers in the sector using a variety of measures. The results of this study demonstrated that despite different possibilities and obstacles, as well as the entry of the private sector, the expansion of public sector undertakings had not slowed.

Gour and Gupta (2012) examined the solvency ratio of Indian life insurance firms during a three-year period, from 2009-10 to 2011-12. The purpose of this study was to see if the performance of different firms was comparable or if there were any notable differences. ICICI was ranked first among chosen businesses of the industry, followed by Birla Sun Life, SBI, HDFC, and LIC, based on the solvency ratio. The article concluded that the solvency of life insurance is determined by the returns gained from total investible money and the rate of interest.

Neelaveni (2012) based on the yearly growth rate, attempted to assess the financial performance of five selected life insurance firms in terms of various plans and policies. The findings of this study showed that the Life Insurance Corporation, as a public entity, was trailing behind owing to fierce competition from private insurers; yet, private life insurance businesses performed well financially during the study period.

Kumari (2013) assessed both the public and private life insurance industries' financial performance. Various characteristics were studied for this purpose, including the number of life insurance firms, private sector offices, insurance penetration and density, premium revenue growth, and the size of the insurance market. Various financial ratios were used to assess financial performance. After privatization, the overall business performance of the Indian life insurance sector improved significantly, according to the report.

Based on regulatory and supervisory norms and standards, Valeed A. Ansari and Wubshet Fola (2014) conducted research to analyze the financial soundness and performance of life insurance businesses in India. The authors used the CAMEL model, which captures the essential functions of life insurance through its parameters. Certainly, proper risk management and a good internal control system, as well as effective and efficient company underwritings, are a summarization of overall financial soundness and performance. It looked at the results of seven registered life insurers during five years, from 2008-09 to 2012-13. The CAMEL model found a considerable difference between private and public life insurance businesses in terms of capital sufficiency, asset quality, management efficiency, profits & profitability, and liquidity situation.

Using the CAMEL model, V.N. Parthiban (2014) sought to assess the soundness and financial performance of life insurers. The CAMEL model was used to assess the financial soundness and performance of life insurers like LIC, SBI, and ICICI Prudential Life, and it was discovered that they are all financially sound. Furthermore, the CAMEL criteria varied substantially across the selected life insurers in India, according to this study.

C Kalpana Naidu and C Paramasivan (2015) attempted to compare LIC and private insurance businesses' financial performance. According to the authors, offering more unit-linked plans allows private companies to gain market share away from LIC. LIC and commercial insurers' investment patterns have also changed. Despite significant losses, private life insurers had a far higher solvency ratio than LIC. Private insurers had a greater capital adequacy ratio than LIC,

although LIC handled death claims better than private life insurance. Finally, this research suggests that private-sector enterprises have outperformed India's LIC.

Maraboina Sreedhar Babu (2015) investigated the performance of commercial and public sector life insurance businesses. In comparison to public-sector insurance businesses, the findings of this study show that private-sector insurance companies must remain competitive by providing cost-effective creative products. The study also found that private-sector life insurance businesses grew their market share more quickly than public-sector life insurance companies during the study period.

Anoop Kumar Singh and Sumbul Fatima (2017) attempted to evaluate ICICI Prudential Life Insurance's performance and discover the causes behind the company's high reputation and market dominance in the life insurance business. This article attempted to assess the development and performance of ICICI Prudential, one of the largest private sector life insurance firms, using several metrics such as net profit, net premium, and branch count. The CAMEL Model was also employed in this study to examine specific ratios such as capital to total assets, net premium to gross premium ratio, and so on. The one-sample t-test is used to further statistically test these results.

Ratios have been used as a basic tool to assess financial statements for a long time, and they are now helpful for comparing financial statements between organizations and throughout time periods (Horrigan, 1968). Financial ratios have become instruments to evaluate corporate appraisals and measure financial soundness, according to Bartoneche & Knight (2001). Furthermore, ratios can be used as a forecasting technique to assess the solvency and creditworthiness of financial institution debtors (Beaver, 1966).

Profitability, efficiency, finance, and liquidity ratios are some of the ratios that may be calculated (Bartoneche & Knight, 2001). Furthermore, in order to evaluate ratios throughout time, a corporation must consider consistent data and techniques while using these ratios (Steffan, 2008). Insurance businesses, in particular, use ratio analyses derived from financial statements to evaluate their financial health. There are a few key ratios to consider, including loss, expenditure, and combined ratio (Outreville, 1998). Furthermore, according to the Record of the Society of Actuaries (1986), the evaluation of financial health takes into account both quantitative and qualitative factors, as employed by rating agency A.M. Best. Profitability, leverage, and liquidity are examples of quantitative fields. Reinsurance capability, reserves adequacy, and management performance are among the qualitative areas (Record of Society of Actuaries, 1986).

The CAMEL framework is a set of financial soundness indicators used in the insurance and banking industries. It is widely utilized and has shown positive outcomes in financial soundness measurement. The CAMEL framework, which adds the reinsurance and actuarial parts to the CAMEL framework, is used to display qualitative soundness indicators in insurance company performance. It's worth noting that some indicators used by banks differ from those utilized by insurance firms in terms of structure and interpretation.

S/N	Variable	Description	Indicator of measurement
1	C	Capital Adequacy	Capital / Total Assets
2	A	Asset Quality	Equities/ Total Assets
3	RA	Reinsurance and actuarial and issues	Net premium / Gross premium
4	M	Management soundness	Operating expenses / gross premium
5	E	Earnings and Profitability	Expenses / net premium Technical reserves Investment income / investment Assets Return of equity (ROE)
6	L	Liquidity	Liquid assets / Current liabilities

In comparison to prior frameworks for the financial evaluation of insurers (Simpson and Damoah; 2008, 12), the CAMELS model has created two main aspects of analysis: managerial soundness and actuarial issues.

According to Das, Davies, and Podpiera (2003), good management is critical in assessing an entity's financial health, and it is critical for insurers' financial stability, despite the fact that finding any direct quantitative measure of management soundness is challenging.

According to Deborah & Deborah (2015), risk-based capital (RBC) is a method used by insurers to determine the minimum capital necessary to maintain their company operations. The more risk an insurer has, the more cash is required to pay the risk (Deborah & Deborah, 2015). The following is the RBC equation:

$$RBC = \frac{\text{Solvency level}}{\text{Minimum capital based on risk}}$$

Solvency is defined as assets minus liabilities, according to Circular Letter Indonesia Financial Services Authority No. 24/SEOJK.05/2017. Deposits, equities, bonds, medium-term notes, real estate investments, repurchase agreements, land and buildings, gold, and policy loans are among the permitted assets. Finally, risk-based minimum capital takes credit, liquidity, market, insurance, and operational risks into account.

As an international rating organization, Standard and Poor's (S&P) has established a Financial Strength Rating model for insurance businesses based on the insurance rating framework. Both quantitative and qualitative criteria are used in this model. The insurance rating structure (Standard and Poor's, 2013) has multiple phases. To begin, S&P assesses insurance firms' commercial and financial risk profiles. S&P (2013) examines industry and country risks as well as competitive positions in order to create a business risk profile. S&P (2013) assesses capital and profits, risk position, and financial flexibility for the financial risk profile. Secondly, S&P looks at enterprise risk management, management, and governance. Thirdly, S&P (2013) has expressed worry about the company's liquidity. For insurance firms, steps one through three can provide a creditworthiness image. Finally, S&P (2013) evaluates government backing for the insurance business before assigning ratings to firms.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The population of the study for this research is made up of all five life insurance companies in Lagos state, Nigeria. They are FBN Insurance, Leadway Assurance, AXA Mansard, African Alliance Insurance Plc, and Custodian Life Assurance Ltd. These insurance companies were chosen based on proximity and accessibility. For the purpose of this research work, the major source of data collection is the annual financial report obtained from the website of the considered insurance companies. The data were downloaded and carefully worked on to meet the objective of this research work.

Ratio analysis and statistical tools most will be utilized to evaluate the hypothesis. Different ratios employed in the CAMEL Model (Capital sufficiency, Asset quality, Reinsurance and Actuarial concerns, Management soundness, Earnings/Profitability, and Liquidity) were used as statistical tools for this study. Statistical tools such as Excel, SPSS, and others are used to test the CAMEL parameters.

CAPITAL ADEQUACY: This metric combines two non-life insurance firm ratios and one life insurance indicator. As a result, prudential regulations have emphasized the need for appropriate capitalization and solvency as critical areas to understand a company's financial status and to maintain a close eye on insurance businesses that see capital sufficiency as the primary indication of financial soundness. Capital adequacy suggests that a company must have a certain amount of capital in order to be financially healthy and make timely payments, however, there are no intentionally agreed capital adequacy rules for insurance companies.

To avoid going bankrupt, the insurance firm must have sufficient capital to cover its losses resulting from claims filed by the insured. It also contributes to the company's financial system's stability and efficiency. The capital adequacy ratio is calculated by using the following formulas:

- Net premium to capital = $\frac{\text{Net premium}}{\text{Capital}}$
- Share capital to Total Asset Ratio = $\frac{\text{Share capital}}{\text{Total asset}}$
- Share capital to Technical Reserve ratio = $\frac{\text{Capital Share}}{\text{Mathematical reserve}}$

$$\text{Share Capital} = \text{Equity share capital} + \text{Reserve and Surplus} - \text{Debit balance of policyholder account} \\ - \text{Debit balance of shareholders account} - \text{miscellaneous expenditure}$$

$$\text{Total assets} = \text{fixed assets} + \text{investment}$$

Technical reserve are taken after the allocation of bonuses.

Net premium to Capital: The amount of premium required to cover solely projected losses before any additional expenditures are loaded. Within the basic set of capital adequacy ratios for non-life insurers, there are two: net premium/capital and capital/total assets. The proper proxy for the quantity of retained indemnity risk is net premium. The ratio is simple to compute and simply requires information from the sources.

Capital to Total Assets Ratio: It reflects the increase in the assets base and the effectiveness of the firm in employing capital in asset development by determining the proportion of capital in the total assets of the company. It also denotes how much of the company's assets are financed by its capital. Because there are no minimum or maximum ratio requirements, it may be advantageous to have a

lower ratio, which signals a superior and stronger asset base, as long as the firm meets the minimum capital need.

Capital to Technical Reserve Ratio: Reserve is a set of funds set aside for a certain purpose. Such specific purposes may include payments to be made for unforeseen circumstances, meeting claims, or any other unexpected expenditure required for the smooth operation of the business, among others, which aids in the smooth operation of the business without jeopardizing the company's profit and loss position. Surplus, on the other hand, is the amount left over in the profit and loss account after dividends, bonuses, taxes, and other expenses have been paid. Such reserves and surpluses are created in the insurance industry so that the insurer is confident in its ability to pay the insured's claims. Insurance firms set up reserves and surplus to cover the costs of claims originating from the policies they sell. However, there are no established restrictions on how much reserve insurance firms should keep aside, but they should set aside enough to cover any losses that may come from the number of policies issued throughout the year. These insurance firms should make such estimates of real losses using the actuaries they hire. As a result, the reserve should be sufficient to meet predicted obligations.

ASSET QUALITY: Asset quality refers to the quality of a company's assets, which determines its financial strength. The asset quality indicators include (*real estate + unquoted equities + debtors*) to total assets ratio, debtors to (*gross premium + reinsurance recoveries ratio*), equities to total assets ratio, and non-performing loans to total gross loans, as shown in the table above. In these ratios, equities are defined as the company's paid-up capital, and total assets are defined as the total application of funds minus the profit and loss account's debit balance. The amount of total assets supported by the company's equity capital is represented by this ratio. A greater asset quality ratio is desired so that the company's financial soundness is preserved and insolvency is avoided since a larger amount will be financed by the firm's equity capital. In contrast, a smaller ratio implies a reduced margin of safety because there is a greater chance of losing money if the assets are of poor quality, which might stymie the company's profitability.

REINSURANCE AND ACTUARIAL ISSUE: The financial soundness indicators of insurance businesses, according to the IMF working paper, include reinsurance and actuarial difficulties, which may be assessed using three (3) ratios. The first is the risk retention ratio, which is calculated by dividing net premium by gross premium; the second is the Net technical reserves to the average of net claims paid over the previous three years; and the third is the Net technical reserves to the average of net premium received over the previous three years.

Risk Retention Ratio: This ratio assists as an indicator of insurance risk management policy of the insurance company. It is worked out by dividing the Net premium by Gross premium. i.e.

$$\text{Risk retention ratio} = \frac{\text{Net premium}}{\text{Gross premium}} \times 100$$

$$\text{Net premium} = \text{Gross premium} - \text{Reinsurance ceded} + \text{Reinsurance accepted}$$

This risk retention ratio shows how well a corporation underwrites its insurance premiums and how much risk it passes on to reinsurers. The difference between the gross and net premiums represents the amount of risk transferred to the reinsurer. The higher the sum, the more risk is passed on to the reinsurer and vice versa, as well as the company's risk carrying ability. It's calculated by dividing the gross premium by the net premium. Net premium is the amount gained after subtracting reinsurance ceded and adding reinsurance accepted from and to gross premium

amount. Gross premium is the total of direct premium and assumed premium written before the effect of ceded reinsurance.

Net Technical Reserves to Average of Net Premium Received in Last Three Years: This ratio represents the amount of reserves established as a percentage of the average net premium earned over the previous three years. The ratio is a measure of how insurance firms' reserves have changed over time. It considers how much money has been set aside for future reasons from the average earnings over the previous three years. Technical reserves are defined as reserves and surpluses, and the average of net premium gained over the previous three years is used to evaluate. The three-year ratio indicates a sufficient mathematical reserve. The formula used for calculating this ratio is as follows: Net Technical Reserves / Average of Net Premium Received in Last three Years

Whereas:

Net Technical Reserves are after the allocation of bonus.

Average net premium received in last three years

$$= \frac{\text{Net premium of year 1} + \text{Net premium of year 2} + \text{Net premium of year 3}}{3}$$

Net premium = Premium received – Reinsurance ceded + Reinsurance accepted

MANAGEMENT SOUNDNESS: The effectiveness of the company's working employees is reflected in the management's soundness. It refers to the company's personnel's efficiency and soundness. The ratio utilized to measure managerial soundness sheds information on these employees' operational efficiency, or how effective and how excellent they are at making decisions that have a positive impact on the organization. The company's administration is good because of its cost efficiency and efficient use of finances. For the company's financial stability, it's critical to keep an eye on managerial soundness. There are two ratios to measure the management soundness of insurance businesses in this area. The first ratio is gross premium to number of employee; and second ratio is assets per employee.

Gross Premium to Number of Employee Ratio: Before the effect of ceded reinsurance, gross premium is the sum of direct and assumed premiums written. Employees are counted as the total number of agents, which includes both individual and corporate agents. Agents are usually in charge of premium collection, although the company's efficiency is determined by all marketing channels as well as the number of employees. The gross premium-to-number-of-employees ratio is used to assess a company's management efficiency. The greater the ratio, the more efficient the company's management is, resulting in a higher quantity of gross premium per number of agents at any one moment.

Asset per Employee Ratio: Total assets are calculated as the total application of money minus the negative balance in the profit and loss account, and they indicate the company's entire strength. The number of workers is based on the annual reports of the individual life insurance. The greater the ratio, the better the firm's situation, implying that the company's employees can endure bigger returns to the company. It also shows that the staff are working hard to strengthen the company's standing.

EARNING AND PROFITABILITY ANALYSIS: The strength of a company's existence in the market is reflected in its earnings and profitability. Earnings are the most important and, in many

cases, the sole long-term source of capital. When profitability is low, it might lead to solvency issues. This ratio study reveals the insurers' potential to generate profits by displaying their market profitability position. It is critical that the many firms in the industry be compared and rated on their profitability. As proposed by the IMF working paper there were numerous ratios to evaluate namely: expense to net premium ratio, return on equity ratio, return on assets ratio, and earnings per employee ratio to measure the performance of insurance companies.

Expense to Net Premium Ratio: The expenditure ratio reflects the company's ability to generate a net premium as well as how much it has spent insuring the net premium. When the company's expenditures are low and earnings are high, the management will demonstrate efficiency and profitability. A lower ratio is preferred since it leads to a bigger profit margin and the company's solid financial condition. To assess life insurers' performance, the researcher divided expenses into two categories: total and operating expenses, and calculated the ratios total expense to net premium ratio and operating expense to net premium ratio.

Total Expense to Net Premium Ratio: The total expense to net premium ratio represents the amount of money spent by the firm to underwrite net premium. It also denotes the company's capacity to be cost-effective and successful in obtaining the net premium. The overall expenditure number comprises operational expenses, commission expenses, and other expenses related to the insurance company. The amount gained after subtracting reinsurance ceded and adding reinsurance accepted from and to the gross premium amount is referred to as the net premium. The higher the profitability, the smaller the ratio. As a result, a smaller ratio is deemed better since it indicates that the firm was cost-effective in insuring net premium and hence had to pay less.

Operating Expense to Net Premium Ratio: The quantity of operational expenditures incurred in underwriting net premiums is represented by the operating expense to net premium ratio. The lower the ratio, the higher the company's profitability. As a result, the operational expenditure is defined as the amount of insurance-related operating expenses, and the net premium is the amount obtained after subtracting reinsurance ceded and adding reinsurance accepted from and to the gross premium amount.

Return on Equity Ratio: The return on equity ratio is one of the earnings and profitability assessments in which it is determined how much a firm earns from the capital invested as equity. It assesses how well a company's management uses its equity share capital to create net profits. The ratio also indicates how well the corporation is using the capital provided by equity owners in its business activities. It's preferable if the ratio is greater. A greater ratio indicates that the firm is profitable and that the equity owners will get more dividends. The net profit is divided by the equity share capital to arrive at this figure. Net profit is profit after taxes, while equity share capital is the amount of money invested as paid-up equity.

Earnings per Employee: Earnings per employee is a profitability analysis ratio that indicates the productivity of a firm by measuring the efficiency of each individual employed in the organization. It also describes how a business's efficient human resource works to produce profits or how well the firm uses its human resources to achieve such profits, indicating the company's employed personnel's expertise. The greater the ratio, the better the company's financial situation as well as its efficiency.

Return on Assets Ratio: The return on assets (ROA) ratio explains a company's capacity to generate a net profit from its total assets. It is calculated by dividing net profit by the company's

total assets. The net profit is the profit after taxes, while total assets are the entire application of money less the profit and loss account's debit balance. The intensity of the company's capital base, which is then used to generate profits, is also referred to as ROA. A greater ratio is preferable since it implies that the firm is effectively utilizing its assets, resulting in larger earnings than the amount invested in assets. In other words, the return on assets ratio measures how well a corporation manages its assets to generate net profits. It assists investors in determining the company's health in terms of how effectively the firm is managed by the company's management.

LIQUIDITY: The timeliness of insurance claims is unpredictable in the insurance industry. It is impossible to forecast when the insured will make a claim on its insurance policy. As a result, the insurer should be prepared to pay out its doubtful claims on this basis. As a result, the insurer must take into account the frequency of claims as well as the nature of the firm. As a result, an insurance company's liquidity condition should be examined. To satisfy its uncertain and unexpected commitments, it needs to maintain its liquidity level. The term "liquidity" refers to a situation in which the payee is ready to pay out as quickly as practicable (basically within one year). In insurance, the insurer must pay claims at the end of the policy's term, which is known in advance, but in the event of unforeseen events, the insurer must call upon its liquid assets to pay for it. As a result, while insurance does not have a significant liquidity crisis compared to banks, it does require a strong liquidity position to sustain the firm's credibility, market share, and reputation. Furthermore, in the case of insurance, a loss of trust nearly always leads to policyholders canceling coverage, demanding a refund of any unused payment, and maybe switching to another insurance firm. The corporation must be aware that a high level of liquidity is a risk since assets may sit idle and money may become entangled in present assets. As a result, a balance must be struck between excessive liquidity and a lack of liquidity.

$$\text{Liquidity} = \frac{\text{liquid assets}}{\text{current liabilities}}$$

Liquid Assets to Current Liabilities: When an asset can be turned into cash promptly or reasonably without losing value, it is considered to be liquid. Other assets include debtors, bill receivables, and marketable securities, with cash being the most liquid. Cash and cash equivalents, government bonds and quoted corporate bonds, and stocks are all examples of liquid assets, according to the IMF working paper. All obligations that are due to maturity within a year are considered current liabilities. Creditors, bills payable, accumulated costs, short-term bank loans, income tax liabilities, and long-term debt expiring in the current year make up this category. A liquid assets to current liabilities ratio of 1:1 is generally regarded as excellent and indicates that a company's financial position is improving.

4. ANALYSIS, RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 1:GROSS PREMIUM

NAME / YEAR	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
AAI	1368277	1747226	3352966	6568953	10078060	13672443	13418189	6295670	5229081	7029956
AXA	7520527	10004767	12444451	13759752	16943161	15009324	17350219	20602218	23026817	28014854
CUSTODIAN	13724295	10061012	13864109	14425865	24003550	27806647	28368403	31997526	36722146	47203260
FBINSURANCE	2566010	2586122	2606234	3898947	7129474	10307383	9909681	19580871	25976164	37625631
LEADWAY	15878667	19120685	25924183	24801444	42111612	46648918	52718567	84479591	87737230	88854306

The above table shows the gross premium of five life insurance companies for a period of ten (10) years (2010-2019).

Table 2: NET PREMIUM

NAME / YEAR	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
AAI	1351416	1805244	3290309	3554197	10011954	13631633	13367745	6246267	5068135	6578607
AXA	3166847	4129396	7109300	7534754	8842563	8664101	8205987	8955599	10416786	12687959
CUSTODIAN	5320717	4025830	7828927	6351027	15928712	17688835	18250591	18812347	20572470	28028224
FBINSURANCE	2561710	2566010	2601934	3894647	7109362	9711296	10488948	19386561	25459483	35803989
LEADWAY	8698205	10027240	12887858	10624230	29901720	39947156	41275055	69823794	71121875	70898107

The above table shows the net premium of five life insurance companies for a period of ten (10) years (2010-2019).

Table 3: OPERATING PREMIUM

NAME / YEAR	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
AAI	713214	836840	960466	1110345	1545501	1715380	12257129	13351126	8003674	16241553
AXA	517316	858430	1120682	1204318	1845372	1882007	1958064	2018202	2479161	2953481
CUSTODIAN	1971777	1457563	1990215	17129561	16596909	20394529	25899457	29987744	34291669	51328405
FBINSURANCE	295025	312461	356506	387987	662431	893887	1217402	1881938	1641713	2346950
LEADWAY	1751749	1926685	2391627	3119971	3818144	3495725	4286250	4853013	6004809	5595554

The above table shows the operating expenses of five life insurance companies for a period of ten (10) years (2010-2019).

Table 4: TOTAL ASSET

NAME / YEAR	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
AAI	13496521	13600322	14837830	16058408	23189358	33278415	41133110	41289651	38927978	37706917
AXA	19891940	23080664	27288052	28789782	34263778	37920073	42076526	50865177	53435737	67597041
CUSTODIAN	16004196	18013383	12137877	10717799	12137878	14501187	15973880	18273532	19922013	21522893
FBINSURANCE	2040583	3060875	7192193	11323511	15454829	20926548	29505399	46945248	70539340	109042132
LEADWAY	39025271	42009403	66324688	97161751	100584648	137368341	166063523	271948637	312768033	394765310

The above table shows the total asset of five life insurance companies for a period of ten (10) years (2010-2019).

Table 5: SHARE CAPITAL

NAME / YEAR	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
AAI	10292500	10292500	10292500	10292500	10292500	10292500	10292500	10292500	10292500	10292500
AXA	5000000	5000000	5000000	5000000	5000000	5000000	5000000	5000000	5000000	5000000
CUSTODIAN	2550424	2550424	2940933	2940933	2940933	2940933	2940933	2940933	2940933	2940933
FBINSURANCE	3480000	3480000	3480000	3480000	3480000	5336450	5336450	5336450	5336450	5336450
LEADWAY	2865436	3139798	4389798	4389798	4389798	4389798	4389798	3139798	5000000	5000000

The above table shows the share capital of five life insurance companies for a period of ten (10) years (2010-2019).

Table 6: EQUITY

NAME / YEAR	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
AAI	8351856	7086215	7594299	4584380	5331865	391825	3381471	281562	2966010	10592307
AXA	13236646	13340286	13443926	13542633	14047595	15397159	14581992	16555564	16767833	23097805
CUSTODIAN	11347750	12576791	11347750	10118709	11347750	13344865	14656653	16674062	18420723	19647017
FBINSURANCE	1989705	2553679	3117653	3681627	4245601	9495858	7783583	9935994	11971756	17837757
LEADWAY	2973324	9967650	11986526	15467171	15962800	20305202	31530745	47060563	45270877	54292233

The above table shows the equity of five life insurance companies for a period of ten (10) years (2010-2019).

Table 7: EXPENSES

NAME / YEAR	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
AAI	249220	222421	399782	625018	852046	1117875	951683	839041	804832	1178148
AXA	106038	192485	1569562	2946638	3674885	3462146	6572707	8226223	7525346	10975875
CUSTODIAN	810764	924622	803866	2216639	1976427	2235387	2488900	2887773	2865306	4036932
FBINSURANCE	829803	985513	1506691	2800829	5418260	7901993	5930967	2917585	4543438	6961246
LEADWAY	92948	210685	3649325	683209	1001368	2079640	2166593	2253546	2759166	3426538

The above table shows the expenses of five life insurance companies for a period of ten (10) years (2010-2019).

Table 8: LIQUID ASSET

NAME / YEAR	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
AAI	4262863	5468519	9044201	12881518	19030299	28359608	36561038	35549658	31788841	32017383
AXA	2846550	4045935	709178	7026175	10340489	13220868	10628630	13740282	26678689	43303982
CUSTODIAN	1577414	2599081	4325342	4058237	5414195	8186875	8860246	10506023	9500516	9318705
FBINSURANCE	63748	2792114	4684844	10624458	12994236	20326682	29054848	46082294	71590275	110718042
LEADWAY	4539517	2196215	19286681	30911963	48705426	87749617	99922569	170087794	197487856	277735417

The above table shows the liquid asset of five life insurance companies for a period of ten (10) years (2010-2019).

Table 9: CURRENT LIABILITY

NAME / YEAR	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
AAI	646088	1946406	3419257	4330679	598663	5389209	6392334	5664496	6708109	64979978
AXA	324991	836686	2606364	2481997	3044320	4164277	4278957	5377994	8521994	10739107
CUSTODIAN	544643	452419	53010	89315	356141	543080	691142	347338	766016	936712
FBINSURANCE	1485968	1830405	2174842	2519279	4235395	10960550	11127427	20587215	31756821	60752290
LEADWAY	1000486	795162	901905	22045149	35022040	70134993	74569226	124687883	156840986	231655249

The above table shows the current liability of five life insurance companies for a period of ten (10) years (2010-2019).

To deduce the capital adequacy, C :

$$C = \frac{\text{capital}}{\text{total asset}}$$

Table 10: CAPITAL ADEQUACY

Name / Year	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	MEAN	RAN K
AAI	0.76260393 3	0.7567835 53	0.6936661 22	0.6409414 93	0.4438458 37	0.3092845 62	0.2502242 11	0.2492755 39	0.2643985 26	0.2729605 29	0.4643984 3	5
AXA	0.25135808 8	0.2166315 49	0.1832303 75	0.1736727 29	0.1459266 98	0.1318562 86	0.1188311 03	0.0982990 78	0.0935703 39	0.0739677 35	0.1487343 98	2
CUSTODIAN	0.15935970 8	0.1415849 54	0.2422938 54	0.2743971 03	0.2422938 34	0.2028063 63	0.1841088 7	0.1609394 94	0.1476222 81	0.1366420 86	0.1892048 55	3
FBINSURANCE	1.70539497 8	1.1369297 99	0.4838579 83	0.3073251 75	0.2251723 39	0.2550086 14	0.1808635 09	0.1136739 12	0.0756521 11	0.0489393 4	0.4532817 76	4
LEADWAY	0.07342514 62	0.0747403 85	0.0661864 85	0.0451803 1	0.0436428 23	0.0319564 03	0.0264344 51	0.0115455 55	0.0159862 88	0.0126657 53	0.0401763 57	1

The above table shows the capital adequacy of five life insurance companies for the period of ten (10) years (2010-2019).

To deduce the Asset quality ratio: A

$$A = \frac{\text{equities}}{\text{Total assets}}$$

Table 11: Asset quality ratio

Name / Year	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	MEAN	RAN K
AAI	0.6188154 71	0.5210328 84	0.5118200 57	0.2854815 99	0.2299272 36	0.0117741 48	0.0822080 07	0.0068191 91	0.0761922 44	0.2809115 1	0.2624982 35	2
AXA	0.6654276 05	0.5779853 65	0.4926671 2	0.4703972 06	0.4099838 32	0.4060424 41	0.3465588 39	0.3254793 35	0.3137943 62	0.3416984 63	0.4350034 57	4
CUSTODIAN	0.7090484 27	0.6981915 06	0.9349040 2	0.9441032 62	0.9349039 43	0.9202601 83	0.9175386 94	0.9124706 71	0.9246416 51	0.9128427 58	0.8808905 11	5
FBINSURANCE	0.9750669 29	0.8342970 56	0.4334773 83	0.3251312 25	0.2747103 19	0.4537708 75	0.2638019 91	0.2116506 87	0.1697174 37	0.1635859 16	0.4105209 82	3
LEADWAY	0.0761897 08	0.2372718 79	0.1807249 51	0.1591899 16	0.1587001 63	0.1478157 33	0.1898715 89	0.1730494 53	0.1447426 6	0.1375304 05	0.1605086 46	1

The above table shows the asset quality ratio of five life insurance companies for the period of ten (10) years (2010-2019).

To deduce the reinsurance and actuarial issues ratio, RA

$$RA = \frac{\text{Net premium}}{\text{gross premium}}$$

Table 12: Reinsurance and Actuarial issue

Name / Year	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	MEAN	RA NK
AAI	0.9876772 03	1.033205 779	0.981312 963	0.541059 892	0.993440 603	0.997015 164	0.996240 625	0.992152 861	0.969220 978	0.935796 326	0.942712 239	4
AXA	0.4210937 61	0.412742 845	0.571282 735	0.547593 736	0.521895 708	0.577247 916	0.472961 58	0.434691 012	0.452376 288	0.452901 129	0.486478 671	1
CUSTODIAN	0.3876859 98	0.400141 656	0.564690 237	0.440252 768	0.663598 176	0.636136 928	0.643342 207	0.587931 298	0.560219 71	0.593777 294	0.547777 627	2
FBINSURANCE	0.9983242 47	0.992223 105	0.998350 11	0.998897 138	0.997179 035	0.942168 929	1.058454 657	0.990076 539	0.980109 419	0.951585 078	0.990736 826	5
LEADWAY	0.5477918 9	0.524418 45	0.497136 515	0.428371 429	0.710058 784	0.856336 175	0.782932 036	0.826516 715	0.810623 666	0.797914 138	0.678209 98	3

The above table shows the reinsurance and actuarial issue ratio of five life insurance companies for the period of ten (10) years (2010-2019).

To deduce the management soundness ratio, M

$$M = \frac{\text{operating expenses}}{\text{gross premium}}$$

Table 13: Management soundness

Name / Year	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	MEAN	RA NK
AAI	0.521249 718	0.478953 495	0.286452 651	0.169029 22	0.153353 026	0.125462 582	0.913471 185	2.120683 899	1.530608 151	2.310334 944	0.860959 887	5
AXA	0.068787 201	0.085802 098	0.090054 756	0.087524 688	0.108915 45	0.125389 191	0.112855 29	0.097960 423	0.107664 077	0.105425 536	0.099037 871	2
CUSTODIAN	0.143670 549	0.144872 404	0.143551 598	1.187420 026	0.691435 6	0.733440 785	0.912968 453	0.937189 456	0.933814 407	1.087391 104	0.691575 438	4
FBINSURANCE	0.114974 221	0.120822 22	0.136789 713	0.099510 714	0.092914 428	0.086722 983	0.122849 767	0.096111 046	0.063200 748	0.062376 363	0.099627 22	3
LEADWAY	0.110320 91	0.100764 434	0.092254 672	0.125797 958	0.090667 249	0.074936 893	0.081304 372	0.057445 981	0.068440 832	0.062974 483	0.086490 778	1

The above table shows the management soundness ratio of five life insurance companies for the period of ten (10) years (2010-2019).

To deduce the earning and profitability ratio, E

$$E = \frac{\text{Expenses}}{\text{Net premium}}$$

Table 14: Earning and profitability

Name / Year	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	MEAN	RA NK
AAI	0.184413 978	0.123208 275	0.121502 874	0.175853 505	0.085102 868	0.082005 949	0.071192 486	0.134326 791	0.158802 4	0.179087 761	0.131549 689	2
AXA	0.033483 777	0.046613 355	0.220775 885	0.391072 887	0.415590 48	0.399596 681	0.800964 832	0.918556 425	0.722424 94	0.865062 3	0.481414 156	5
CUSTODIAN	0.152378 711	0.229672 391	0.102678 949	0.349020 56	0.124079 524	0.126372 766	0.136373 666	0.153504 132	0.139278 657	0.144030 96	0.165739 032	3
FBINSURANCE	0.323925 425	0.384064 365	0.579065 803	0.719148 359	0.762130 273	0.813690 881	0.565449 176	0.150495 232	0.178457 591	0.194426 548	0.467085 365	4
LEADWAY	0.010685 883	0.021011 265	0.283159 932	0.064306 684	0.033488 642	0.052059 776	0.052491 584	0.032274 757	0.038794 9	0.048330 458	0.063660 388	1

The above table shows the earning and profitability ratio of five life insurance companies for the period of ten (10) years (2010-2019).

To deduce the liquidity ratio, L

$$L = \frac{\text{liquid asset}}{\text{current liability}}$$

Table 15: Liquidity

Name / Year	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	MEAN	RA NK
AAI	6.597960 34	2.809546 929	2.645077 863	2.974479 983	31.78799 926	5.262295 079	5.719513 092	6.275873 087	4.738867 689	0.492726 898	4.930434 022	4
AXA	8.758857 938	4.835667 144	0.272094 765	2.830855 557	3.396649 827	3.174829 148	2.483930 079	2.554908 391	3.130568 855	4.032363 399	3.547072 51	2
CUSTODIAN	2.896234 781	5.744853 775	81.59483 116	45.43735 095	15.20239 175	15.07489 688	12.81971 867	30.24726 059	12.40250 334	9.948313 889	23.13683 558	5
FBINSURANCE	0.042899 982	1.525407 765	2.154107 747	4.217261 367	3.068010 422	1.854531 205	2.611102 099	2.238393 78	2.254327 503	1.822450 512	2.178849 238	1
LEADWAY	4.537311 866	2.761971 774	21.38438 195	1.402211 57	1.390707 851	1.251153 144	1.339997 401	1.364108 443	1.259159 745	1.198917 004	3.788992 075	3

The above table shows the liquidity ratio of five life insurance companies for the period of ten (10) years (2010-2019).

Table 16: OVERALL RANKING

Name	C	A	RA	M	E	L	Avg.	Rank
AAI	5	2	4	5	2	4	3.67	4
AXA	2	4	1	2	5	2	2.67	2
CUSTODIAN	3	5	2	4	3	5	3.67	4
FBINSURANCE	4	3	5	3	4	1	3.33	3
LEADWAY	1	1	3	1	1	3	1.67	1

Hence the overall ranking of all the five (5) life insurance companies is been computed in the table above.

ANALYSING OTHER PARAMETERS

Table 17: RISK RETENTION RATIO

Name / Year	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	MEAN	RA NK
AAI	98.76772 028	103.3205 779	98.13129 629	54.10598 919	99.34406 027	99.70151 64	99.62406 253	99.21528 606	96.92209 778	93.57963 265	94.27122 393	4
AXA	42.10937 611	41.27428 455	57.12827 348	54.75937 357	52.18957 077	57.72479 16	47.29615 805	43.46910 124	45.23762 88	45.29011 288	48.64786 71	1
CUSTODIAN	38.76859 977	40.01416 557	56.46902 372	44.02527 761	66.35981 761	63.61369 28	64.33422 072	58.79312 982	56.02197 105	59.37772 942	54.77776 273	2
FBINSURANCE	99.83242 466	99.22231 047	99.83501 098	99.88971 381	99.71790 345	94.21689 288	105.8454 657	99.00765 395	98.01094 188	95.15850 777	99.07368 255	5
LEADWAY	54.77918 896	52.44184 505	49.71365 154	42.83714 287	71.00587 838	85.63361 748	78.29320 361	82.65167 146	81.06236 657	79.79141 382	67.82099 797	3

The above table shows the risk retention ratio (RRR) of the five insurance company been considered in this research for a duration of ten years.

Table 18: EXPENSE TO NET PREMIUM RATIO

Name / Year	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	MEAN	RAN K
AAI	0.1844139 78	0.1232082 75	0.1215028 74	0.1758535 05	0.0851028 68	0.0820059 49	0.0711924 86	0.1343267 91	0.1588024	0.1790877 61	0.1315496 89	2
AXA	0.0334837 77	0.0466133 55	0.2207758 85	0.3910728 87	0.4155904 8	0.3995966 81	0.8009648 32	0.9185564 25	0.7224249 4	0.8650623	0.4814141 56	5
CUSTODIAN	0.1523787 11	0.2296723 91	0.1026789 49	0.3490205 6	0.1240795 24	0.1263727 66	0.1363736 66	0.1535041 32	0.1392786 57	0.1440309 6	0.1657390 32	3
FBINSURANCE	0.3239254 25	0.3840643 65	0.5790658 03	0.7191483 59	0.7621302 73	0.8136908 81	0.5654491 76	0.1504952 32	0.1784575 91	0.1944265 48	0.4670853 65	4
LEADWAY	0.0106858 83	0.0210112 65	0.2831599 32	0.0643066 84	0.0334886 42	0.0520597 76	0.0524915 84	0.0322747 57	0.0387949	0.0483304 58	0.0636603 88	1

The above table shows the expense to net premium ratio (ENP) of the five insurance company been considered in this research for a duration of ten years.

Table 19: RETURN ON EQUITY RATIO

Name / Year	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	MEAN	RAN K
AAI	0.161810261	0.254754336	0.433260397	0.775284117	1.877758345	34.79010528	3.953233667	22.18433951	1.708738339	0.621074049	6.676035829	5
AXA	0.239248447	0.309543289	0.528811301	0.5563729	0.629471664	0.56270777	0.562748011	0.540941946	0.621236268	0.549314491	0.510039609	1
CUSTODIAN	0.468878588	0.320099936	0.68991007	0.627651907	1.403689013	1.325516219	1.245208643	1.128240197	1.116811213	1.426589288	0.975259508	2
FBINSURANCE	1.287482315	1.00482872	0.834581013	1.057860288	1.67452429	1.022687576	1.347573219	1.951144596	2.126628959	2.007202419	1.43145134	3
LEADWAY	2.925414452	1.00597834	1.075195432	0.686889025	1.87321272	1.967336055	1.30904154	1.483700779	1.571029318	1.305860951	1.520365861	4

The above table shows the return on equity ratio (ROE) of the five insurance company been considered in this research for a duration of ten years.

TEST OF HYPOTHESES

The analysis in this study started with a descriptive analysis of liquidity and capital adequacy by insurance companies. Table 20 shows the mean and standard deviation of liquidity and capital adequacy for each insurance company.

Table 20: Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Liquidity		Capital Adequacy	
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation
AAI	10	5.00	2.18	0.46	0.22
AXA	10	3.55	2.18	0.15	0.06
CUSTODIAN	10	23.14	24.04	0.19	0.05
FB INSURANCE	10	2.18	1.07	0.45	0.54
LEADWAY	10	3.79	6.27	0.04	0.02
Total	50	7.53	13.35	0.26	0.31

For liquidity, AAI had an average of 5.00 ($SD = 2.18$), AXA had an average of 3.55 ($SD = 2.18$), CUSTODIAN had an average of 23.14 ($SD = 24.04$), FB INSURANCE had an average of 2.18 ($SD = 1.07$) while LEADWAY had an average of 3.79 ($SD = 6.27$). For capital adequacy, AAI had an average of 0.46 ($SD = 0.22$), AXA had an average of 0.15 ($SD = 0.06$), CUSTODIAN had an average of 0.19 ($SD = 0.05$), FB INSURANCE had an average of 0.45 ($SD = 0.54$) while LEADWAY had an average of 0.04 ($SD = 0.02$).

And to determine the impact of insurance company on the liquidity and capital adequacy, a one way ANOVA test will be carried out. The table below gives the ANOVA analysis:

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Capital Adequacy	Between Groups	1.448	4	.362	5.170	.002
	Within Groups	3.152	45	.070		
	Total	4.601	49			
Liquidity	Between Groups	3084.908	4	771.227	6.142	.000
	Within Groups	5650.806	45	125.573		
	Total	8735.715	49			

From the above table 21, there is a significant difference in the capital adequacy of the 5 insurance companies as $p = 0.002$ and also there is a significant difference in the liquidity of the 5 insurance companies as $p = 0.000$ as well. This means that the null hypothesis is rejected for this analysis. To probe further, other analysis were carried out.

First, Levene test for equality of variances was carried out on liquidity and capital adequacy and the results were presented in the table 22 below. And from the table 22, there were significant differences among the variances of liquidity of the 5 insurance companies, $F(4, 45) = 3.403$, $p = .016$.

		Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
Liquidity	Based on Mean	9.542	4	45	0.000
	Based on Median	3.403	4	45	0.016
Capital Adequacy	Based on Mean	9.703	4	45	0.000
	Based on Median	3.516	4	45	0.014

Similarly, there were significant differences among the variances of capital adequacy of the 5 insurance companies, $F(4, 45) = 3.516$, $p = .014$. Though the null hypothesis for the parameters is rejected but this test shows that the assumption of equality of variances had been violated. Also, the normality tests were carried out on the liquidity and capital adequacy. The results are presented in the table 23 below:

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a					
	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Liquidity	0.301	50	0.000	0.484	50	0.000
Capital Adequacy	0.280	50	0.000	0.672	50	0.000

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

The Shapiro-Wilk test for normality above revealed that liquidity is not normally distributed ($p < 0.05$) and capital adequacy is not normally distributed ($p < 0.05$). This shows that the normality assumption had been violated. This is also evidenced in the figures shown below:

And as a result, the usual one way ANOVA test might not be reliable enough. Hence, the Welch test for unequal variances was carried and this was followed by Game Howell's post hoc test to compare the differences in liquidity and capital adequacy among the insurance companies. The Welch tests were carried out for liquidity and capital adequacy and the summary was presented in the table 24 below:

Table 24: Robust Tests of Equality of Means				
Liquidity				
	Statistic ^a	df1	df2	Sig.
Welch	5.001	4	20.655	0.006
Capital_Adequacy				
	Statistic ^a	df1	df2	Sig.
Welch	28.327	4	20.447	0.000
a. Asymptotically F distributed.				

And from the table above, the Welch test is significant for liquidity, $F(4, 21) = 5.001$, $p = 0.006$. Similarly, the Welch test is significant for capital adequacy, $F(4, 20) = 28.327$, $p < .001$. This implies that the null hypotheses will be rejected and it can be concluded that the mean of liquidity of at least one insurance company differs significantly from the mean of liquidity of other insurance companies. Similarly, the mean of capital adequacy of at least one insurance company differs significantly from the mean of capital adequacy of other insurance companies.

Due to limitation of the one way ANOVA test not revealing the insurance companies that differ in liquidity and capital adequacy, there is need for a post hoc test. And the appropriate post hoc test was Game Howell's post hoc test which was summarized in the table below:

Table 25: Multiple Comparisons						
Dependent Variable: Liquidity						
Games-Howell						
Insurance Company		Mean Difference	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
AAI	AXA	1.449	0.97444	0.583	-1.4975	4.3955
	CUSTODIAN	-18.141	7.63276	0.205	-43.7177	7.4357
	FB INSURANCE	2.817*	0.76771	0.020	0.4035	5.2305
	LEADWAY	1.207	2.09928	0.976	-5.5674	7.9814
Dependent Variable: Capital Adequacy						
Games-Howell						
Insurance Company		Mean Difference	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
AAI	AXA	.31566*	0.07309	0.010	0.0759	0.5554
	CUSTODIAN	.27519*	0.07249	0.023	0.0359	0.5144
	FB INSURANCE	0.01112	0.18547	1.000	-0.5802	0.6024
	LEADWAY	.42422*	0.07125	0.001	0.1859	0.6626

From table 24 above, AAI and FB INSURANCE differ significantly in liquidity, $p = .02$ but other pairs of two insurance companies were not significant because their corresponding p-value were greater than 0.05 level of significant. Furthermore, AAI and AXA differ significantly in capital adequacy, $p = .01$. Also, AAI and CUSTODIAN differ significantly in capital adequacy, $p = .023$ and AAI and LEADWAY differ significantly in capital adequacy, $p = .001$.

5. CONCLUSION

The following findings can be summarized from the analyzed data. They are:

- Having a low capital adequacy ratio threatens the long-term survival of the life insurance company been considered.
- The low asset quality ratio deduced that most life insurance companies depend on external sources for financing their assets.
- The high risk retention ratio deduced that insurers rarely opt for reinsurance. So rather than pay for reinsurance, those companies reinvest their premium to yield more returns and enable more timely settlements of claims. From the descriptive analyses been carried out, FB Insurance has a high risk retention ratio which means there is a further profitability investment opportunities in their life insurance business which result in an increase in stock price.

- African Alliance Insurance Plc have a greater return on equity. It shows equity owner in the insurance company gains more dividend compared to AXA Mansard that offers less dividends to their equity owner in the company.
- Leadway Assurance has the healthiest management (i.e. least expenses on gross premium) and overall financially sound life insurance company. The low expenses ratio of Leadway assurance indicates cost effective operations which boost profitability and also Leadway assurance have a low ENP ratio which indicates that they will have a bigger profit margin compared to other insurance company and this put them in a position of a positive financial conditions.
- FBN Insurance is the most liquid and also FBN Insurance has a high retention ratio which means that there is a further profitability investment opportunities in their life insurance business which result in an increase in stock price.

It is difficult to assess the financial health of an individual insurer or the insurance industry as a whole. To attain an acceptable level of dependability, it must consider both quantitative and qualitative indicators. As a result, the study adopted the CAMEL model, which uses multiple indices to assess the health of the insurance market. This included analysis on major areas, which include Capital Adequacy, Asset Quality, Reinsurance, and Actuarial problems, Management soundness, Earnings/Profitability, and Liquidity. It aids in the monitoring and management of the insurance company's financial performance by insisting on the appearance of difficulties. To control and administer the insurance business, the user must be aware of the data accuracy and underlying assumptions.

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